

**METHODS OF TEACHING YOUNG PEOPLE TO PLAY THE SPORT OF
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The article discusses the stages and methods of teaching children to play badminton. As we know, the load on the body that occurs when playing badminton helps to reduce the amount of "bad" cholesterol in the blood. This, in turn, increases life expectancy and improves the functioning of the cardiovascular system. The manifestations of tachycardia and other heart ailments decrease. At the same time, modern children, regardless of age, are characterized by limitation of physical activity, deterioration in physical qualities of strength, speed, endurance, agility, flexibility, as well as spatial orientation and vestibular stability. If we consider badminton from different points of view, then the game has a lot of positive and almost no negative. Badminton, one of the sports games that preschool children can master all the elements.

Key words: teaching methodology, badminton, development, speed, quickness, endurance, agility, flexibility.

In the 19th century, British officers serving in India became interested in the ancient Indian game of purne, which can be considered the prototype of modern badminton. The British brought their passion for the game to their homeland. The modern tradition of the game originates in England, in the old Badminton House, whose owner, famous sports enthusiast and publisher of a series of books on sports, Charles Somerset, 8th Duke of Beaufort, built the first badminton court in 1873. In 1893, the Badminton Association of England published the first regulation of the official rules of the game. Analysis of the research of teachers, still the last century, concerning the development of motor abilities and qualities of children EN Vavilova, 1981; N.A.Notkina, 1980; Yu. K. Chernyshenko, 1999, has already testified that about 40% of older preschoolers have a level of development of motor abilities below average. The experience of practicing teachers shows Adashkevichene E.Y., Grishin V.V., Frolov V.G., Yurko G.P., Zmanovsky Yu.V. and others that preschool children can master elements of various sports games (basketball , football, volleyball, table tennis, badminton, hockey, etc.). At the same

time, modern children, regardless of age, are characterized by limited physical activity, deterioration of physical qualities of strength, speed, endurance, agility, flexibility, as well as spatial orientation and vestibular stability [2].

Badminton, one of the sports games that preschool children can master all the elements. Badminton is a sports game that requires agility and speed from the players. You need rackets and shuttlecock to play. First, children need to be introduced to the features of the shuttlecock flight: unevenness, variability of the direction of flight, dependence on the force of impact. To do this, the children throw the shuttlecock up and catch it, and then toss to each other (on the spot, while walking, running). These exercises develop an eye, dexterity. When the guys master these exercises, they are taught to use a shuttlecock and a racket. The teacher shows how to hold the racket. Hand grasp the racket handle close to the end so that you can freely move your hand during the strike. An angle should form between your thumb and forefinger. In order to check the grip, the hand with the racket is brought forward. The head of the racket must be perpendicular to the surface of the court. The shuttlecock is hit from the right and left sides, as well as from above and below. Starting position: feet on shoulder-width apart, slightly bent in knees. The hand with the racket is directed forward and up, the rim is at shoulder level perpendicular to the ground. Actions with a shuttlecock and a racket: while standing still, tap the shuttlecock, turning the racket with one side and the other; hitting a shuttlecock suspended from a string; beat the shuttle, throwing it over the net. Play in pairs: one child has a racket, the other has a shuttlecock. One child throws a shuttlecock on the racket, the other hits it (distance 3m). When children master these skills, they can play in tandem with each other, in the future, preschoolers can play badminton through the net. The game continues until one of the players scores 10 points. Badminton is a great game available to many [1].

This game is played in almost every yard, on the beaches and during picnics. Probably, there is not a single person who has not tried to play badminton at least once. If we consider badminton from different points of view, then the game has a lot of positive and almost no negative. Badminton does not require expensive equipment. It is much easier to equip a badminton court than, for example, for tennis. In addition, badminton in Europe, especially in Denmark, the game of badminton has become very popular precisely because of its simplicity and lack of additional costs. And people of any age can play it [4].

This game requires little physical effort, therefore it is recommended for children, adults and even older people. Badminton improves reaction and coordination of movements, develops the muscles of the arms, legs, trunk, helps to straighten the spine, trains the

cardiovascular system and respiratory system, improves mood. This game can be beneficial, heal the body in case of chronic diseases. For therapeutic purposes, badminton is recommended to increase the range of motion in the joints. Badminton seems to be very similar to tennis, but much less popular. But it looks like this only at first glance. In fact, it is one of those sports that the whole family enjoys, whether they play badminton professionally or just throw a shuttlecock during the summer holidays. But at the same time, while playing badminton, there are so many jumps and movements that it can be equated to a run of 5-10 kilometers! Even more surprising is that among playing sports, it is badminton that takes the third place in terms of loads [5].

The stress on the body, which occurs when playing badminton, helps to reduce the amount of "bad" cholesterol in the blood. This, in turn, increases life expectancy and improves the functioning of the cardiovascular system. The manifestations of tachycardia and other heart ailments decrease, the heart muscle itself becomes stronger. The heart is strengthened, and the person develops endurance. In addition, frequent badminton activity lowers blood pressure and decreases the number of heart beats per minute.

A sequence of movements mastering is proposed:

- acquaintance with the shuttlecock (preparatory exercises - throws, catching the shuttlecock);
- learning to grip the racket, open and closed side;
- juggling shuttlecock;
- training in badminton stance;
- teaching the technique of strikes with a racket on the right, left, overhead;
- learning to serve shuttlecock;
- play paired with a coach;
- play paired with a partner;

When familiarizing with the shuttle, exercises were used to develop the feeling of the shuttle (its speed and trajectory of flight, as well as to develop dexterity and speed. This is tossing the shuttle up (alternately with the right and left hand) and catching it with two hands, one hand. shuttlecock from front to back above the head (back) After the throw, you need to turn 180 ° and catch the shuttle. Throws are performed alternately with the right and left hand. To increase the density of the lesson, exercises were carried out with two shuttlecocks, since they increase the number of movements performed by each hand, harmoniously develop the right and left parts of the body, learn to quickly switch attention (gaze) from one object to another, develop quickness and dexterity [6].

When learning to grip the racket, attention was paid to how the child holds the racket, as an incorrect position limits impacts and leads to the appearance of bruises on the forearm. In addition, with an incorrect grip, the racket becomes shorter, and, therefore, the distance to the shuttle that the player can reach is also smaller. It was also necessary to ensure that the child did not hold the racket like a frying pan. This position severely limits the range of motion of the racket head, especially in overhead strikes, as it limits the mobility in the wrist joint. With such a grip, it is impossible to hit the shuttlecock along a steep path from top to bottom. In addition, it will be difficult to execute individual strikes [7].

It was also important to pay attention to the position of the child's index finger, if the finger is straightened and located along the racket, then the support on the hand will weaken when performing blows from above and from the right, because of which they will be weaker and will be produced with a delay. We must not forget about the thumb. If it is on the upper side of the handle and touches it with the lower surface of the nail phalanx, then the support on the hand weakens when hitting from the left and below, and when hitting from above, the racket will fly out of the hands. When juggling a shuttlecock, it was necessary to pay special attention to the directionality of the racket's grip, to make sure that the contact with the shuttle was at the level of the head and above, and not at the level of the belt, especially when juggling with the closed side, and also that the elbow was not raised high. It is necessary to draw the child's attention to the need to move in order to position himself more comfortably in relation to the shuttlecock, not to look away from the shuttlecock at the moment of contact with it (look in the direction of the expected flight of the shuttlecock). The children had to be explained that when serving, the racket should only move forward, and the shuttle should go diagonally and fall within the bounds of the opponent's corresponding field of service. At the moment of impact, the shuttle must be completely below the server's belt, and the racket shaft must be sloped downward. They switched to playing in pairs after learning and consolidating the basic actions with a shuttlecock and a racket. In pair games, children tried to combine the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities. Games for preschoolers with a shuttlecock and a racket (badminton).

1. "Catch the shuttlecock" The aim of the game: to accurately pass the shuttlecock and catch it in the air. Description of the game. The game is played in four subgroups standing in circles. In the center of each circle is the driver. Children throw the shuttlecock to each other, trying to prevent the driver from touching or catching him. If the driver catches the shuttlecock, then the player who unsuccessfully threw the shuttlecock stands in the place of the driver, and

the driver takes his place. Methodical techniques. The instructor makes sure that the children do not hold the shuttlecock for a long time, do not throw it to the same child. If the driver cannot catch the shuttle for a long time, a new one is appointed. The game can be complicated: introduce two drivers and throw two shuttlecocks.

2. "From racket to racket." Purpose of the game: to improve the ability to pass and receive the shuttlecock on the racket. Description of the game. The game involves two children. One is holding a shuttlecock, the other is holding two-racks. The first one puts the shuttlecock on the second child's right racket. He should play the shuttle up, but beat it off with his left racket. Then vice versa. After that, the children change objects. Methodical techniques. The game can be played by distributing children into teams (subgroups). The team that completed the task more accurately wins. Options. - The same, but moving forward with a step, in fast walking.

3. "Protect the basket from the shuttlecock." Purpose of the game: to hit the shuttlecock with a racket in different directions. Description of the game. Children form 4 circles. In the center of the circle there is a basket, next to the basket - the driver, he has a racket. Each player has a shuttlecock in his hands. At the signal of the teacher, the children alternately throw the shuttlecocks into the basket, trying to get into it. The driver protects the basket by reflecting the shuttlecocks with a racket, beating them in any direction. The player, whose shuttle is repulsed, picks it up (or catches it in the air) and takes its place. If the child hits the basket with a shuttle, then he gets 3 points. If, within 2 minutes, the driver managed to protect the basket from shuttlecocks, then it is considered that he coped well with his role. The best team is the one that strictly followed the rules of the game. Methodical techniques. The teacher monitors the timely change of the drivers, advises the drivers to beat the shuttlecock not very hard, and to all the players he offers to throw the shuttlecock slowly, as if aiming.

The options are:

- Throw a shuttlecock at the same time to two or more players from different sides.
- Perform the task with your left hand. Thus, badminton will be a great help for hypertensive patients, and for the rest
- optimal prevention.

Of course, playing badminton affects more than just the cardiovascular system. The work of the lungs improves, a lot of calories are burned from constant movement, so badminton classes will be useful for those who dream of losing weight or adjusting their figure. During the game, a person involuntarily performs a whole complex of movements, due to which body

weight is reduced, excess fat deposits are burned. The muscles in the abdomen are strengthened and tightened, joint mobility develops, and posture is leveled. As practice has shown, such changes do not go unnoticed. Seniors who regularly practice badminton live longer than those who are sedentary. After all, their internal organs begin to function normally by improving blood flow. Due to the fact that badminton classes almost always take place in the fresh air, the body is enriched with oxygen, which gives a good sound sleep. All this together

relieves irritability, depression and blues. If you already have osteoporosis, it is better to consult a doctor before starting to practice badminton, but if you only have a risk of this disease, then badminton will be an excellent prevention. Physical activity can reduce the risk of not only numerous diseases of the spine and bones, but also reduce the likelihood of some cancers. At the same time, the load during badminton is quite within the power of both youth and children, and

To old people. Experts note that significant positive changes also occur in diabetes. Many people have low blood sugar levels. And watching a flying shuttle helps to develop a reaction and trains the muscles of the eyes well. This makes it possible to avoid vision problems that appear from constant stress at the computer or while reading. Badminton classes allow you to establish a normal breathing rhythm. For people suffering from respiratory diseases, they become a kind of panacea. This is evidenced by many examples when badminton helps to defeat even asthma. Among other things, playing badminton gives positive emotions and improves well-being. Perhaps now it becomes clear why badminton has been included in the Olympic Games since 1992. So, once again going to "leave the shuttlecock", know that you are not only doing a very healthy, but also an Olympic sport. The massive development of this sport helps to solve the main task facing the physical culture movement: to achieve the physical perfection of our people, to strengthen their health, to ensure creative longevity, to prepare for the defense of the Motherland. Badminton classes allow a versatile effect on the human body, develop strength, speed, endurance, improve joint mobility, promote

acquiring a wide range of motor skills, educate volitional qualities. The activity of a badminton player has a beneficial effect on the anatomical and physiological structure. Simplicity, accessibility make it possible for people of any age and gender to practice badminton, using the simplest grounds or terrain for this. Spectacularity, effective impact on the body predetermined the inclusion of this sport in the system of physical education in schools, secondary and higher educational institutions. Wide possibilities of load variability allow using badminton as a rehabilitation tool in rest homes, in various groups of general physical training.

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